

USE OF MEDIA TECHNOLOGIES TO IMPROVE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASIS OF CREATIVE APPROACH

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Reforms in the social sphere on the basis of a creative approach, the use of media literacy in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions, the implementation of foreign advanced separations in order to achieve the heights of modern science and technology, while first feeling the need for knowledge, level of not only young people, but also members of our entire society.

Indeed, in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach, innovation, adaptation requires the time itself to work in conditions, to be more rigid in relation to rapidly changing conditions. Therefore, educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach the use of media literacy in improvement, radical reform of Education, Promotion of this system to a new qualitative stage important.

Creative approach, creative competence in pedagogical dictionaries (ing. "sreate" means creativity, creativity). This type of competence is related to having skills such as innovation, creativity and organization. Separately, it should be noted that creativity is not only for the creation of new ideas, but also for raising the lifestyle and spirituality of the individual also of great importance. The use of media literacy in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach to improving the quality and effectiveness of Education acts as a foundation when increasing. Media, Internet, television, radio, cinema, video, which are becoming the essence of our life in the organization of educational activities of students in higher educational institutions, the phone and other means of communication also have an impact. Attention to the positive aspects of media literacy skills to focus on, these technologies enable student youth to receive, analyze, evaluate and create Media texts helps in the formation of abilities. If we pay attention to the lexical meaning of the concept of "media literacy". West media pedagogues interpret the concept of "media literacy" (media literacy) as follows: "media literacy" - to students and students in communicating with the media, it helps to take a critical look at the understanding of the media content in their lives. Media literacy critical and analytical approach of a student or student in assessing media text, at a critical distance in a relationship with popular culture the ability to interpret, analyze and create Media text [6;] "media literacy"- the ability to interpret, analyze and create Media text "Media literacy" - the ability to receive, analyze, evaluate and transmit information of various forms [8;] "media literacy" - media literacy man in the modern world, coded and representation understanding the socio-cultural, political context of the media operating in the systems, perception, creation of Media text, the process of analysis, preparation for evaluation. [5;] "media literacy" - the cultural significance of audiovisual and printed texts to humans, a motivating action to help you understand, create and evaluate the content. Every person can become a media literacy [7;]

The result of our analysis and observations of pedagogical literature indicates that there are non-traditional methods of Education, pedagogical technology, advanced national and international in social pedagogy and psychology based on experience, a personal example in life, planning one's own activities, compliance with the rules of a healthy lifestyle, compatibility of need and opportunity, knowing the result in advance setting a goal, pedagogical skills and techniques play an important role.

As stated in scientific sources, every educator can become a psychologist, find a way to the hearts of young people, and also keep up with the Times formation of a worldview (work on oneself in accordance with the worldview of young people), as to moral authorities or as a socially active person, relying on the requirements of his country must operate. Studies show that there are issues in this regard that is waiting for some specific solution.

In particular, in higher educational institutions, the Organization of "days of spirituality", "information hour", spiritual and educational events is organized on the basis of a certain mold. It is of course good. Today, however, "satisfied" student youth with "yesterday's information", "messages in the mold will not be. The formation of a culture of information analysis in student youth in educational institutions for socio-spiritual protection each educator who operates is equally responsible and responsible. Therefore, with the fact that a modern pedagogue is a master of his profession in addition, "psychologist", "actor", "artist", "technologist "should be" parents", students can enter the " world " of education and upbringing plays an important pedagogical role in ensuring its effectiveness.

Educational work carried out on the basis of media literacy the effectiveness of pedagogical and psychological study of the student's personality is associated with knowledge of their individual typological characteristics. The study is organized on the basis of a special program and in which the personality of the student factors of upbringing and fate, experience of communication with people, environment, and attitude to what is happening, Labor, internal and the external world, behavior, level of consciousness and thinking, morality should be reflected. He is in the culture, perception and thinking of student youth, manifested in needs, interests, character and temperament, habits, features of thinking, communication, and attitude.

Only then is it possible to find out which group of students belongs or inclinations and determine the paths of educational influence. [3;]

In our opinion, the technical and scientific growth of today, if, on the one hand, the student shows his influence on the lifestyle of young people, on the second hand, it is precisely it that creates new threats to human life (living in a virtual being, psychologically virtual asset preference, virtual threats v.b.). In this regard, to the organization of educational activities in higher educational institutions the attitude in the preparation is actually becoming the main category of the formation of national and ideological immunity.

It should be noted that special attention is paid to youth education in our country, "the systematic reform of Higher Education setting priorities, having modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities, highly qualified with independent thinking raising the process of training personnel to a qualitatively new level", they are ideological and legal, so to speak, the growth of technical literacy in common with. [1;] the problem is that socio-political, economic and cultural reforms are being implemented in our society, it is especially relevant in the current period when the renewal process is going on. Because it is rich in Universal Events, intellectual and informational the media education system that is developing technologies is

developing, the propaganda of dirt in Western media, its own the original goal of moving the model of Democracy Forward is the provisions of [4; 48] in the current era, which are coming with the youth spirituality, spiritual, moral education, from which to have a high level of secular culture requires are you looking for.

The fact that the student youth has a high level of secular culture is directly the process of educating the culture of reading in them it is desirable to spend in harmony with. Our analysis and observations of pedagogical literature showed that the use of media literacy in the educational process contributes to the theoretical and practical assimilation of the subject to the students ' perception of a particular novelty.

It is worth saying that the use of media and information technology is always a favorable pedagogical environment for educators to develop, master the skills of creativity and creativity creates. The use of media literacy in the educational process is the main factor that ensures the freedom and development of individual creativity.

In this regard, the approach is to increase the intellectual potential of educators, the skills of creative activity in them development should become the first level task of the educational process. In doing so, it is advisable to proceed as follows:

- ensuring independence for the emergence of creative opportunities of educators;
- development of a mechanism of mutual unity between new types of education and advanced educational tools; (based on the essence of the topic taking into account the age characteristics of students, – educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach the emergence of social necessity by ensuring continuity in improvement;
- creation of advanced educational tools in the use of media literacy in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach;
- justification of technologies (methods) for the use of advanced educational tools in the use of media technologies in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach;
- creation of a system of principles of Education (New didactic rules) in the use of media literacy in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions on the basis of a creative approach.

In conclusion, on the basis of a creative approach, the purpose of educational activities in the use of media literacy in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions and based on the content and educational materials of the curriculum are determined. In this regard, the classification of students ' activities related to working with educational materials, as well as the educational situations in which they are organized are clearly taken into account, plays an important pedagogical role in determining the purpose of training and lessons in improving educational activities in higher educational institutions.

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